

Using *OpenSimRoot* to model faba bean root growth

Problem

Root structure and root–soil–environment interactions are central to root research, yet traditional experimental approaches are time-consuming, resource-intensive, and sensitive to environmental variability. This limits the systematic exploration of root traits and their functional consequences.

Solution

The growth of faba bean root systems is simulated with *OpenSimRoot*, a software for functional-structural plant modelling in 3D soil.

Benefits

Coupling structure and function allows to link morphological changes to physiological processes, providing mechanistic explanations of plant behaviour. *OpenSimRoot* can be used to explore potential breeding targets, assess existing genotypes and test management or environmental scenarios without the cost and variability of field experiments.

Applicability box

Theme: Root modelling toolbox

Keywords: Faba bean (*Vicia faba L*), root growth, functional-structural plant model (FSPM), root system architecture (RSA), simulation

Context: Simulations across regions and environments

Required time:

Data collection: weeks to months (experiments and literature)

Installation: within minutes

Simulation: from minutes to hours

Equipment: Computer with *OpenSimRoot* and Paraview for visualisation
Software/hardware for data acquisition/analysis, e.g., RhizoVision Explorer or WinRhizo

Practical application

The model is available upon request. This section focuses on defining key parameters for the required input file to set up a faba bean model in *OpenSimRoot* (Figure 1); an applied example of model execution is provided in the barley model and interested users are encouraged to contact the modeling team for access and further guidance.

- **Root classes:** Identify and define root classes for faba bean: primary root, epicotyl-born roots, lateral roots from epicotyl-born roots, lateral roots from primary root, and second-order lateral roots (Figure 1).
- **Shoot traits:** Determine shoot- and photosynthesis-related traits, including leaf growth rate, leaf senescence, specific leaf area, extinction coefficient, and light-use-efficiency.
- **Root traits:** Specify class-specific traits, including growth rate, diameter, density, root hair, root angle, branching density, and faba bean-specific secondary growth.
- **Carbon modules:** Add carbon-related modules by defining parameters for root exudates, shoot and root respiration, and carbon allocation to shoot and root.
- **Water & nutrient uptake:** Parameterise water and nutrient uptake processes, including radial and axial hydraulic conductivities and Michaelis-Menten parameters (V_{max} , K_m , C_{min}) for N, P, and K uptake. Include faba bean-specific biological N-fixation via root nodules.

Figure 1: 3D faba bean root architectures after 80 days of growth. Colors show root age, ranging from dark blue (<1 day old) to red (>70 days old).

Further information

- Root2Res. (2025) Using OpenSimRoot to simulate barley root growth to identify stress-resilient traits. <https://zenodo.org/records/17738404>
- Root2Res. (2025) Using OpenSimRoot to model sweet potato root growth. <https://zenodo.org/records/17738430>
- Postma, J.A., Kuppe, C., Owen, M.R., Mellor, N., Griffiths, M., Bennett, M.J., Lynch, J.P. and Watt, M. (2017), OpenSimRoot: widening the scope and application of root architectural models. *New Phytol*, 215: 1274-1286. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.14641>
- Postma J.A. & Black K. (2020) CH02 - Advances in root architectural modeling during the last decade. In *Understanding and improving crop root function. Advances in modelling plant root systems*, p. 34. Burleigh Dodds Science Publishing, UK. <http://dx.doi.org/10.19103/AS.2020.0075.02>
- Schäfer, E.D., Owen, M.R., Postma, J.A., Kuppe, C., Black, C.K., Lynch, J.P. (2022). Simulating Crop Root Systems Using OpenSimRoot. In: Lucas, M. (eds) *Plant Systems Biology. Methods in Molecular Biology*, vol 2395. Humana, New York, NY. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-0716-1816-5_15
- OpenSimRoot weblink: <https://rootmodels.gitlab.io/>

About this practice abstract and Root2Resilience

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Root2Resilience: The project is running from September 2022 to August 2027. The overall goal of Root2Resilience – Root phenotyping and genetic improvement for rotational crops resilient to environmental change – is to develop root phenotyping, genetic and modelling tools and use them to define and test innovative genotype ideotypes able to enhance the tolerance to abiotic stress and carbon sequestration in soils.

Project website: root2res.eu

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